

Universal Magic Squares of Type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ Using the Digits 2 and 5

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*The whole work is without use of any
programming language.*

Abstract

*This work brings **magic squares** of type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ only for two digits 2 and 5. Each magic square contains 12-digits in each cell. Just with two digits, one can have exactly 1024 different possibilities of 12-digits combinations from two digits. In case of $4k$, we have written **magic squares** of orders: 4, 8, ..., 60 and 64. In case $6k$, we have written **magic squares** of orders: 6, 12, ..., 54 and 60. In case $12k$, we have written magic square of orders: 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60. All the blocks of magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 12 are with **equal sums** in each case. The same work for the digits 1 and 8 is done in Taneja [42], and for the digits 6 and 9 can be seen in Taneja [43]. The work on multiples of 3, 5, 7, etc. shall be dealt elsewhere. Later, the work shall be extended up to magic squares of order 128 having 14-digits in each cell just with two digits, either {1,8}, {2,5} and {6,9}. In the first two cases the work is always **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while in the third case for the digits 6 and 9, the work is only **upside-down**. When the **magic squares** are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, we call them as **universal magic squares**. In order to have **universal magic squares**, the digits 2 and 5 are written in digital form. The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just based on the number's combinations.*

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1 Introduction

In the previous papers [38, 39, 40], the author worked with three groups of numbers for the magic squares of orders 3 to 32. In each group there are only two digits, i.e., {1, 8}, {2, 5} and {6, 9}. In the first and second cases, we have results as **upside-down**

and **mirror looking**, while in the third case for the digits {6, 9}, the results are only **upside-down**. In the second group with the digits {2, 5}, the numbers 2 and 5 are written in digital form to have the conditions for **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. In the third case, 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6, when we make 180° rotation. **Palindromic-type magic squares** are also constructed for the orders 3 to 16 [38].

The whole work is based on combination of two digits. For example, 2-digits combinations of two letters a and b gives us 4 possibilities, i.e., aa, ab, ba, bb . In the similar way, considering 3 by 3 combinations of two letters, there are 8 possibilities, i.e., $aaa, aab, aac, abb, acc, abc, bbb, ccc$. Complete details of these combinations are given in [38, 39, 40].

This work is for the magic squares multiples of 4, 6 and 12, i.e., of type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ using just two numbers. In case of multiples of 4, we have written magic squares of orders 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36, 40, 44, 48, 52, 56, 60 and 64. In case of multiple of 6, we have written magic squares of orders 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54 and 60. In case of multiples of 12 we have written magic squares of orders 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60. These constructions are based on **equal sum magic squares** of orders 4, 6 and 12 in each case. Each one with 12-digits combinations of 2 and 5 in each cell. These magic squares are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, i.e., **universal magic squares**. In case of magic squares of multiples of 4 and 12, all the magic squares are **pandiagonal**. We observe that multiples of 12 are already presents in multiples of 4 and 6. The difference here in multiples of 12 is that these are formed by **semi-magic squares** of order 3, with **different magic sums** resulting in a **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 12 with **equal magic sums**. Similar kind of work for the digits 1 and 8, and 6 and 9 is given in another papers [42, 43]. The work for the multiples of 3, 5, 7, etc., and the **bimagic** cases for the multiples of order 8, 9, 16, etc. shall be dealt later on.

The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just with number's combinations. The study of magic squares of orders 65 to 128 shall be given in another works.

1.1 Blocks of 4

Making 6-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 2 and 5, there are total 64 possibilities. Let's divided these 64 numbers 16 groups of 4 each in such a way that the groups are of equal sums. See below:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
222222	252525	222225	222255	222522	222252	552525	225225	522252	225552	252552	522552	222525	552522	222552	552252
555555	525252	255555	225555	552555	525555	225252	255255	525552	522255	522525	255225	252555	225255	522555	525522
225522	255552	522222	552222	555255	555525	252522	552552	252225	552225	525225	222555	525222	252252	255222	225525
552255	522225	555552	555522	225222	252222	525255	522522	255525	255522	255252	555222	555252	525525	555225	252255
1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554

Let's see how above number's sum become when we write as **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

- **Upside-down Numbers**

The table below give the values when we make 180° rotation:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
222222	525252	522222	552222	225222	252222	525255	522522	252225	255522	255252	255225	525222	225255	255222	252255
555555	252525	555552	555522	555255	555525	252522	552552	255525	552225	525225	522552	555252	552522	555225	225525
225522	255552	222225	222255	552555	525555	225252	255255	522252	522255	522525	555222	222525	252252	222552	525522
552255	522225	255555	225555	222522	222252	552525	225225	525552	225552	252552	222555	252555	525525	522555	552252
1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554

• **Mirror Looking Numbers**

The table below give values when we see the numbers in **mirror**. In this case, 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
555555	525252	255555	225555	552555	525555	252522	255255	525552	522255	522525	522552	252555	552522	522555	525522
222222	252525	222225	222255	222522	222252	525255	225225	522252	225552	252552	255225	222525	225255	222552	552252
552255	255552	555552	555522	225222	252222	552525	522522	255525	255522	255252	222555	555252	525525	555225	252255
225522	522225	522222	552222	555255	555525	225252	552552	252225	552225	525225	555222	525222	252252	255222	225525
1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554	1555554

In this case the numbers are written in digital form to have the **mirror looking** possibilities. Thus we observe from the above three tables that the numbers in each group are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. Thus, we can say that each group is **universal** in itself. Making combinations of 16 groups with each other, it lead us to 256 possibilities with 16 with 16 members each of 12-digits numbers using only 2 and 5. This gives the possibilities of constrcting 256 **universal pandiagonal magic squares** of order 4 with **equal magic sums** $S_{4 \times 4}^n := 155555555554, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 256$. These magic squares are given in Appendix as Section 5, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.1.

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)	193=(1,13)	209=(1,14)	225=(1,15)	241=(1,16)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)	194=(2,13)	210=(2,14)	226=(2,15)	242=(2,16)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)	195=(3,13)	211=(3,14)	227=(3,15)	243=(3,16)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)	196=(4,13)	212=(4,14)	228=(4,15)	244=(4,16)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)	197=(5,13)	213=(5,14)	229=(5,15)	245=(5,16)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)	198=(6,13)	214=(6,14)	230=(6,15)	246=(6,16)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)	199=(7,13)	215=(7,14)	231=(7,15)	247=(7,16)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)	200=(8,13)	216=(8,14)	232=(8,15)	248=(8,16)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)	201=(9,13)	217=(9,14)	233=(9,15)	249=(9,16)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)	202=(10,13)	218=(10,14)	234=(10,15)	250=(10,16)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)	203=(11,13)	219=(11,14)	235=(11,15)	251=(11,16)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)	204=(12,13)	220=(12,14)	236=(12,15)	252=(12,16)
13=(13,1)	29=(13,2)	45=(13,3)	61=(13,4)	77=(13,5)	93=(13,6)	109=(13,7)	125=(13,8)	141=(13,9)	157=(13,10)	173=(13,11)	189=(13,12)	205=(13,13)	221=(13,14)	237=(13,15)	253=(13,16)
14=(14,1)	30=(14,2)	46=(14,3)	62=(14,4)	78=(14,5)	94=(14,6)	110=(14,7)	126=(14,8)	142=(14,9)	158=(14,10)	174=(14,11)	190=(14,12)	206=(14,13)	222=(14,14)	238=(14,15)	254=(14,16)
15=(15,1)	31=(15,2)	47=(15,3)	63=(15,4)	89=(15,5)	95=(15,6)	111=(15,7)	127=(15,8)	143=(15,9)	159=(15,10)	175=(15,11)	191=(15,12)	207=(15,13)	223=(15,14)	239=(15,15)	255=(15,16)
16=(16,1)	32=(16,2)	48=(16,3)	64=(16,4)	80=(16,5)	96=(16,6)	112=(16,7)	128=(16,8)	144=(16,9)	160=(16,10)	176=(16,11)	192=(16,12)	208=(16,13)	224=(16,14)	240=(16,15)	256=(16,16)

1.2 Blocks of 6

As we have seen above, making 6-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 2 and 5, there are total 64 possibilities. Let's consider 60 numbers in 10 groups of 6 each in such a way that the groups are of **equal sums**. See below:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	5	9	10
222255	222522	552552	522252	222252	225552	252552	222552	222525	552252
225555	552555	522522	525552	525555	522255	522525	522555	252555	525522
552222	555255	225225	252225	555525	552225	525225	255222	525222	225525
555522	225222	255255	255525	252222	255522	255252	555225	555252	252255
222222	225522	255552	252525	252252	222555	522552	552522	552525	252522
555555	552255	522225	525252	525525	555222	255225	225255	225252	525255
2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331

Let's see the **upside-down** and **mirror looking** situation of each group.

• Upside-down Numbers

The table below give the values when we make 180° **rotation** in the original numbers as given above:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	5	9	10
552222	225222	255255	252225	252222	255522	255252	255222	525222	252255
555522	555255	225225	255525	555525	552225	525225	555225	555252	225525
222255	552555	522522	522252	525555	522255	522525	222552	222525	525522
225555	222522	552552	525552	222252	225552	252552	522555	252555	552252
222222	225522	255552	525252	252252	555222	255225	225255	525255	225252
555555	552255	522225	252525	525525	222555	522552	552522	252522	552525
2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331

• Mirror Looking Numbers

The table below give values when we see the numbers in **mirror**. In this case, 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	5	9	10
225555	552555	522522	525552	525555	522255	522525	522555	252555	525522
222255	222522	552552	522252	222252	225552	252552	222552	222525	552252
555522	225222	255255	255525	252222	255522	255252	555225	555252	252255
552222	555255	225225	252225	555525	552225	525225	255222	525222	225525
555555	552255	522225	252525	525525	222555	522552	552522	252522	552525
222222	225522	255552	525252	252252	555222	255225	225255	525255	225252
2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331	2333331

In this case the numbers are written in digital form to have the situation of **mirror looking**. Thus we observe from the above three tables that the numbers in each group are **upside-down** and **mirror looking** with **equal sums**. Thus, we can say that each group is **universal** in itself. The same happens with all the 10 groups. Making combinations of 10 groups with each other, it lead us to 100 possibilities with 36 members in each group of 12-digits numbers. Thus, we can construct 100 **universal magic squares** of order 6 with **equal magic sums** $S_{6 \times 6}^n := 2999999999997, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 100$. These magic squares are given in Appendix 6, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.2.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1=(1,1)	11=(1,2)	21=(1,3)	31=(1,4)	41=(1,5)	51=(1,6)	61=(1,7)	71=(1,8)	81=(1,9)	91=(1,10)
2=(2,1)	12=(2,2)	22=(2,3)	32=(2,4)	42=(2,5)	52=(2,6)	62=(2,7)	72=(2,8)	82=(2,9)	92=(2,10)
3=(3,1)	13=(3,2)	23=(3,3)	33=(3,4)	43=(3,5)	53=(3,6)	63=(3,7)	73=(3,8)	83=(3,9)	93=(3,10)
4=(4,1)	14=(4,2)	24=(4,3)	34=(4,4)	44=(4,5)	54=(4,6)	64=(4,7)	74=(4,8)	84=(4,9)	94=(4,10)
5=(5,1)	15=(5,2)	25=(5,3)	34=(5,4)	45=(5,5)	55=(5,6)	65=(5,7)	75=(5,8)	85=(5,9)	95=(5,10)
6=(6,1)	16=(6,2)	26=(6,3)	36=(6,4)	46=(6,5)	56=(6,6)	66=(6,7)	76=(6,8)	86=(6,9)	96=(6,10)
7=(7,1)	17=(7,2)	27=(7,3)	37=(7,4)	47=(7,5)	57=(7,6)	67=(7,7)	77=(7,8)	87=(7,9)	97=(7,10)
8=(8,1)	18=(8,2)	28=(8,3)	38=(8,4)	48=(8,5)	58=(8,6)	68=(8,7)	78=(8,8)	88=(8,9)	98=(8,10)
9=(9,1)	19=(9,2)	29=(9,3)	39=(9,4)	49=(9,5)	59=(9,6)	69=(9,7)	79=(9,8)	89=(9,9)	99=(9,10)
10=(10,1)	20=(10,2)	30=(10,3)	40=(10,4)	50=(10,5)	60=(10,6)	70=(10,7)	80=(10,8)	90=(10,9)	100=(10,10)

1.3 Blocks of 12

As we have seen above, making 6-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 1 and 8, there are total 64 possibilities. Let's consider 60 numbers in 5 groups of 12 each in such a way that the groups are of **equal sums**. See below:

1	2	3	4	5
222222	222252	225225	222555	222525
225522	222255	225252	225552	222552
225525	222522	252225	252552	225255
252255	225222	252522	255225	252252
252525	225555	255255	255252	252555
255552	252222	255525	255522	255222
522225	525555	522252	522255	522555
525252	552222	522522	522525	525222
525522	552555	525255	522552	525525
552252	555255	525552	525225	552522
552255	555522	552525	552225	555225
555555	555525	552552	555222	555252
4666662	4666662	4666662	4666662	4666662

The above groups are considered in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers. Making possible combinations, these 5 groups, it lead us to 25 magic squares of order 12 with equal **magic sums** $S_{12 \times 12}^n := 4666666666662$, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5 . These magic squares are given in Appendix 7, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 1.3.

1	2	3	4	5
1=(1,1)	6=(1,2)	11=(1,3)	16=(1,4)	21=(1,5)
2=(2,1)	7=(2,2)	12=(2,3)	17=(2,4)	22=(2,5)
3=(3,1)	8=(3,2)	13=(3,3)	18=(3,4)	23=(3,5)
4=(4,1)	9=(4,2)	14=(4,3)	19=(4,4)	24=(4,5)
5=(5,1)	10=(5,2)	15=(5,3)	20=(5,4)	25=(5,5)

2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4

In Appendix 5 there are total 256 magic squares of order 4. All of them are **universal pandiagonal magic squares** with **magic sums** $S_{4 \times 4}^n := 155555555554$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 256$. Let's write the Table 1.1 in the following way:

Figure 2.1.

The following subsections lead us to **universal pandiagonal magic squares** multiples of 4, i.e., of orders 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36, 40, 44, 48, 52, 56, 60 and 64. These are chosen according to colors appearing in the Figure 2.1.

2.1 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8

Example 1. Let's consider 4 magic squares of order 4 of type 2×2 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$

In this case, we get following **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 8 with magic sum $S_{8 \times 8} := 31111111108$.

8×8	pan	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	
		225522552255	552255555555	222222222222	555555225522	255552552255	522225555555	252525222222	525252225522	31111111108
31111111108		222222225522	555555222222	225522555555	552255552255	25252225522	525252222222	255552555555	522225552255	31111111108
31111111108		555555555555	222222552255	552255225522	225522222222	525252555555	252525552255	522225225522	255552222222	31111111108
31111111108		552255222222	225522225522	555555552255	222222555555	522225222222	255552225522	525252552255	252525555555	31111111108
31111111108		225522522225	552255525252	222222252525	555555255552	255552522225	522225525252	252525252525	252522555552	31111111108
31111111108		222222555552	555555252525	225522525252	552255522225	252525255552	525252252525	255552525252	522225522225	31111111108
31111111108		55555525252	222222522225	552255255552	225522252525	525252525252	252525222225	522225255552	255552252525	31111111108
31111111108		552255252525	225522255552	555555222225	222222525252	522225252525	255552255552	525252522225	252525525252	31111111108
		31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	31111111108	

2.2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 12

Example 2. Let's consider 9 magic squares of order 4 of type 3×3 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$

In this case, we get following **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 12 with magic sum $S_{12 \times 12} := 466666666662$.

12x12	pan	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	
		225522552255	552255555555	222222222222	555555225522	255552552255	522225555555	252525222222	525252225522	255555522255	522225555555	222225222222	555552225522	466666666662
466666666662		222222225522	555552222222	225522555555	552255552255	252525225522	525252222222	255552555555	522225552255	222225225522	555552222222	255555555555	522225522555	466666666662
466666666662		555555555555	222222552255	552255225522	225522222222	525252555555	252525552255	522225225522	255552222222	555552555555	222225522555	522222255222	255552222222	466666666662
466666666662		552255222222	225522225522	555555522255	222225555555	522225222222	255552225522	525252552255	252525555555	522222222222	255552255222	555552552255	222225555555	466666666662
466666666662		225522522225	552255525252	222222525252	555552555522	255552522225	522225252525	252525252525	525252555522	255555222225	522225252525	222225252525	555552255522	466666666662
466666666662		222222555522	555552525252	225522525252	552255522225	252525555522	525252252525	255552525252	522225222225	222225255522	555552525252	255555252525	522225222225	466666666662
466666666662		555552525252	222222522225	552255555222	225522252525	525252525252	252525222225	522225255522	255552252525	555552525252	222225222225	522222555522	255552525252	466666666662
466666666662		552255252525	225522255522	555555222225	222222525252	522225252525	255552252525	525252522225	252525252525	522222252525	255552555522	555552522225	222225252525	466666666662
466666666662		225522522222	552255555522	222222222225	555552555555	255552522222	522225555522	252525222225	525252255555	255555222222	522225555522	222225222225	555552255555	466666666662
466666666662		222222555555	555552222225	225522555522	552255522222	252525255555	525252222225	255552555522	522225222222	222225255555	555552222225	255555555522	522225222222	466666666662
466666666662		555555555522	222222522222	552255255555	225522222225	525252555522	252525222222	522225255555	255552222225	555552555522	222225222222	522222555555	255552222225	466666666662
466666666662		552255222225	225522255555	555555222222	222222555552	522225222225	255552252525	525252522222	252525555522	522222222225	255552555555	555552522222	222225555522	466666666662
		466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	466666666662	

2.3 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 16

Example 3. Let's consider 16 magic squares of order 4 of type 4×4 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$

In this case, we get following **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 16 with magic sum $S_{16 \times 16} := 6222222222216$. It is given below in two parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$	$145=(1,10)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$	$146=(2,10)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$	$147=(3,10)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$	$148=(4,10)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$	$149=(5,10)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$	$150=(6,10)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$	$151=(7,10)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$	$152=(8,10)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$	$153=(9,10)$
$10=(10,1)$	$26=(10,2)$	$42=(10,3)$	$58=(10,4)$	$74=(10,5)$	$90=(10,6)$	$106=(10,7)$	$122=(10,8)$	$138=(10,9)$	$154=(10,10)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 40 with magic sum $S_{40 \times 40} := 15555555555540$. It is given below in four parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$	$145=(1,10)$	$161=(1,11)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$	$146=(2,10)$	$162=(2,11)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$	$147=(3,10)$	$163=(3,11)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$	$148=(4,10)$	$164=(4,11)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$	$149=(5,10)$	$165=(5,11)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$	$150=(6,10)$	$166=(6,11)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$	$151=(7,10)$	$167=(7,11)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$	$152=(8,10)$	$168=(8,11)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$	$153=(9,10)$	$169=(9,11)$
$10=(10,1)$	$26=(10,2)$	$42=(10,3)$	$58=(10,4)$	$74=(10,5)$	$90=(10,6)$	$106=(10,7)$	$122=(10,8)$	$138=(10,9)$	$154=(10,10)$	$170=(10,11)$
$11=(11,1)$	$27=(11,2)$	$43=(11,3)$	$59=(11,4)$	$75=(11,5)$	$91=(11,6)$	$107=(11,7)$	$123=(11,8)$	$139=(11,9)$	$155=(11,10)$	$171=(11,11)$

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 44 with magic sum $S_{44 \times 44} := 17111111111094$. It is given below in four parts.

2.11 Universal Pandigonal Magic Squares of Order 48

Example 11. Let's consider 144 magic squares of order 4 of type 12×12 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 48 with magic sum $S_{48 \times 48} := 18666666666648$. It is given below in four parts.

$1=(1,1)$	$17=(1,2)$	$33=(1,3)$	$49=(1,4)$	$65=(1,5)$	$81=(1,6)$	$97=(1,7)$	$113=(1,8)$	$129=(1,9)$	$145=(1,10)$	$161=(1,11)$	$177=(1,12)$	$193=(1,13)$
$2=(2,1)$	$18=(2,2)$	$34=(2,3)$	$50=(2,4)$	$66=(2,5)$	$82=(2,6)$	$98=(2,7)$	$114=(2,8)$	$130=(2,9)$	$146=(2,10)$	$162=(2,11)$	$178=(2,12)$	$194=(2,13)$
$3=(3,1)$	$19=(3,2)$	$35=(3,3)$	$51=(3,4)$	$67=(3,5)$	$83=(3,6)$	$99=(3,7)$	$115=(3,8)$	$131=(3,9)$	$147=(3,10)$	$163=(3,11)$	$179=(3,12)$	$195=(3,13)$
$4=(4,1)$	$20=(4,2)$	$36=(4,3)$	$52=(4,4)$	$68=(4,5)$	$84=(4,6)$	$100=(4,7)$	$116=(4,8)$	$132=(4,9)$	$148=(4,10)$	$164=(4,11)$	$180=(4,12)$	$196=(4,13)$
$5=(5,1)$	$21=(5,2)$	$37=(5,3)$	$53=(5,4)$	$69=(5,5)$	$85=(5,6)$	$101=(5,7)$	$117=(5,8)$	$133=(5,9)$	$149=(5,10)$	$165=(5,11)$	$181=(5,12)$	$197=(5,13)$
$6=(6,1)$	$22=(6,2)$	$38=(6,3)$	$54=(6,4)$	$70=(6,5)$	$86=(6,6)$	$102=(6,7)$	$118=(6,8)$	$134=(6,9)$	$150=(6,10)$	$166=(6,11)$	$182=(6,12)$	$198=(6,13)$
$7=(7,1)$	$23=(7,2)$	$39=(7,3)$	$55=(7,4)$	$71=(7,5)$	$87=(7,6)$	$103=(7,7)$	$119=(7,8)$	$135=(7,9)$	$151=(7,10)$	$167=(7,11)$	$183=(7,12)$	$199=(7,13)$
$8=(8,1)$	$24=(8,2)$	$40=(8,3)$	$56=(8,4)$	$72=(8,5)$	$88=(8,6)$	$104=(8,7)$	$120=(8,8)$	$136=(8,9)$	$152=(8,10)$	$168=(8,11)$	$184=(8,12)$	$200=(8,13)$
$9=(9,1)$	$25=(9,2)$	$41=(9,3)$	$57=(9,4)$	$73=(9,5)$	$89=(9,6)$	$105=(9,7)$	$121=(9,8)$	$137=(9,9)$	$153=(9,10)$	$169=(9,11)$	$185=(9,12)$	$201=(9,13)$
$10=(10,1)$	$26=(10,2)$	$42=(10,3)$	$58=(10,4)$	$74=(10,5)$	$90=(10,6)$	$106=(10,7)$	$122=(10,8)$	$138=(10,9)$	$154=(10,10)$	$170=(10,11)$	$186=(10,12)$	$202=(10,13)$
$11=(11,1)$	$27=(11,2)$	$43=(11,3)$	$59=(11,4)$	$75=(11,5)$	$91=(11,6)$	$107=(11,7)$	$123=(11,8)$	$139=(11,9)$	$155=(11,10)$	$171=(11,11)$	$187=(11,12)$	$203=(11,13)$
$12=(12,1)$	$28=(12,2)$	$44=(12,3)$	$60=(12,4)$	$76=(12,5)$	$92=(12,6)$	$108=(12,7)$	$124=(12,8)$	$140=(12,9)$	$156=(12,10)$	$172=(12,11)$	$188=(12,12)$	$204=(12,13)$
$13=(13,1)$	$29=(13,2)$	$45=(13,3)$	$61=(13,4)$	$77=(13,5)$	$93=(13,6)$	$109=(13,7)$	$125=(13,8)$	$141=(13,9)$	$157=(13,10)$	$173=(13,11)$	$189=(13,12)$	$205=(13,13)$

*In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 52 with magic sum $S_{52 \times 52} := 20222222222202$. It is given below in five parts.*

2.13 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 56

Example 13. Let's consider 196 magic squares of order 4 of type 14×14 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)	193=(1,13)	193=(1,14)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)	194=(2,13)	193=(2,14)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)	195=(3,13)	193=(3,14)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)	196=(4,13)	193=(4,14)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)	197=(5,13)	193=(5,14)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)	198=(6,13)	193=(6,14)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)	199=(7,13)	193=(7,14)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)	200=(8,13)	193=(8,14)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)	201=(9,13)	193=(9,14)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)	202=(10,13)	193=(10,14)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)	203=(11,13)	193=(11,14)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)	204=(12,13)	193=(12,14)
13=(13,1)	29=(13,2)	45=(13,3)	61=(13,4)	77=(13,5)	93=(13,6)	109=(13,7)	125=(13,8)	141=(13,9)	157=(13,10)	173=(13,11)	189=(13,12)	205=(13,13)	193=(13,14)
14=(14,1)	30=(14,2)	46=(14,3)	62=(14,4)	78=(14,5)	94=(14,6)	110=(14,7)	126=(14,8)	142=(14,9)	158=(14,10)	174=(14,11)	190=(14,12)	206=(14,13)	193=(14,14)

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 56 with magic sum $S_{56 \times 56} := 21777777777756$. It is given below in six parts.

2.14 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 60

Example 14. Let's consider 225 magic squares of order 4 of type 15×15 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or a part of Figure 2.1 as given below:

1=(1,1)	17=(1,2)	33=(1,3)	49=(1,4)	65=(1,5)	81=(1,6)	97=(1,7)	113=(1,8)	129=(1,9)	145=(1,10)	161=(1,11)	177=(1,12)	193=(1,13)	209=(1,14)	225=(1,15)
2=(2,1)	18=(2,2)	34=(2,3)	50=(2,4)	66=(2,5)	82=(2,6)	98=(2,7)	114=(2,8)	130=(2,9)	146=(2,10)	162=(2,11)	178=(2,12)	194=(2,13)	210=(2,14)	226=(2,15)
3=(3,1)	19=(3,2)	35=(3,3)	51=(3,4)	67=(3,5)	83=(3,6)	99=(3,7)	115=(3,8)	131=(3,9)	147=(3,10)	163=(3,11)	179=(3,12)	195=(3,13)	211=(3,14)	227=(3,15)
4=(4,1)	20=(4,2)	36=(4,3)	52=(4,4)	68=(4,5)	84=(4,6)	100=(4,7)	116=(4,8)	132=(4,9)	148=(4,10)	164=(4,11)	180=(4,12)	196=(4,13)	212=(4,14)	228=(4,15)
5=(5,1)	21=(5,2)	37=(5,3)	53=(5,4)	69=(5,5)	85=(5,6)	101=(5,7)	117=(5,8)	133=(5,9)	149=(5,10)	165=(5,11)	181=(5,12)	197=(5,13)	213=(5,14)	229=(5,15)
6=(6,1)	22=(6,2)	38=(6,3)	54=(6,4)	70=(6,5)	86=(6,6)	102=(6,7)	118=(6,8)	134=(6,9)	150=(6,10)	166=(6,11)	182=(6,12)	198=(6,13)	214=(6,14)	230=(6,15)
7=(7,1)	23=(7,2)	39=(7,3)	55=(7,4)	71=(7,5)	87=(7,6)	103=(7,7)	119=(7,8)	135=(7,9)	151=(7,10)	167=(7,11)	183=(7,12)	199=(7,13)	215=(7,14)	231=(7,15)
8=(8,1)	24=(8,2)	40=(8,3)	56=(8,4)	72=(8,5)	88=(8,6)	104=(8,7)	120=(8,8)	136=(8,9)	152=(8,10)	168=(8,11)	184=(8,12)	200=(8,13)	216=(8,14)	232=(8,15)
9=(9,1)	25=(9,2)	41=(9,3)	57=(9,4)	73=(9,5)	89=(9,6)	105=(9,7)	121=(9,8)	137=(9,9)	153=(9,10)	169=(9,11)	185=(9,12)	201=(9,13)	217=(9,14)	233=(9,15)
10=(10,1)	26=(10,2)	42=(10,3)	58=(10,4)	74=(10,5)	90=(10,6)	106=(10,7)	122=(10,8)	138=(10,9)	154=(10,10)	170=(10,11)	186=(10,12)	202=(10,13)	218=(10,14)	234=(10,15)
11=(11,1)	27=(11,2)	43=(11,3)	59=(11,4)	75=(11,5)	91=(11,6)	107=(11,7)	123=(11,8)	139=(11,9)	155=(11,10)	171=(11,11)	187=(11,12)	203=(11,13)	219=(11,14)	235=(11,15)
12=(12,1)	28=(12,2)	44=(12,3)	60=(12,4)	76=(12,5)	92=(12,6)	108=(12,7)	124=(12,8)	140=(12,9)	156=(12,10)	172=(12,11)	188=(12,12)	204=(12,13)	220=(12,14)	236=(12,15)
13=(13,1)	29=(13,2)	45=(13,3)	61=(13,4)	77=(13,5)	93=(13,6)	109=(13,7)	125=(13,8)	141=(13,9)	157=(13,10)	173=(13,11)	189=(13,12)	205=(13,13)	221=(13,14)	237=(13,15)
14=(14,1)	30=(14,2)	46=(14,3)	62=(14,4)	78=(14,5)	94=(14,6)	110=(14,7)	126=(14,8)	142=(14,9)	158=(14,10)	174=(14,11)	190=(14,12)	206=(14,13)	222=(14,14)	238=(14,15)
15=(15,1)	31=(15,2)	47=(15,3)	63=(15,4)	89=(15,5)	95=(15,6)	111=(15,7)	127=(15,8)	143=(15,9)	159=(15,10)	175=(15,11)	191=(15,12)	207=(15,13)	223=(15,14)	239=(15,15)

In this case, we get a **universal pandiagonal magic square of order 60 with magic sum $S_{60 \times 60} := 23333333333310$** . It is given below in six parts.

2.15 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 64

Example 15. *Let's consider all the 256 magic squares of order 4 of type 16×16 given in Appendix 5 according to Table 1.1 or Figure 2.1, we have a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 64 with magic sum $S_{64 \times 64} := 248888888888864$. It is given below in six parts:*

